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The Heat That Slows the Mind

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In classrooms bright, the sun does blaze,
Its fiery touch, a burning haze.
The heat seeps in, both slow and fast,
And learning seems like a distant past.

The students sit, their faces flush,
The heat makes thoughts a weary hush.
With sweat on brows and sleepy eyes,
The eager minds can't reach the skies.

The books lie open, words do blur,
The voices drone, like distant purr.
The fans spin slow, the air stands still,
A heavy warmth, a stubborn will.

The heat distracts, the minds drift far,
To thoughts of ice and cool, cool jars.
The lessons fade, the focus breaks,
The bright ideas, the heat just takes.

Outside, the shade calls out their names,
The cooling trees, the gentle frames.
But in the room, the sun's embrace,
It steals the joy; it takes the grace.

The teachers speak, their voices clear,
But through the heat, they disappear.
The children long for breeze and shade,
A cooling touch, a gentle trade.

For when the heat is high and strong,
The hours in class feel twice as long.
The learning slows, the minds retreat,
The battle lost to summer's heat.

So as the sun pours down its light,
In midday's heat, so hot and bright,
The students yearn for cooler days,
When learning flows in breezy ways.

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